

Decoupling of Time and Space in Quantum Mechanics

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In quantum mechanics, it is often stressed that if one knows position (x) with complete certainty, then momentum (p) is completely uncertain. A similar result is applied to energy and time. It is also stressed that quantum mechanics is mathematically a wave type theory describing probability waves. In a previous note (1), we argued that one may obtain the Schrodinger equation from $\exp(i \text{ Action})$, where Action is the classical action, by varying x and t in $v=x/t$ independently. A main idea of classical mechanics is that x and t are not independent, but are directly linked i.e. $x(t)$.

In this note, we argue that wave behaviour in quantum mechanics and in the wave equation for a photon decouples time and space which is the opposite notion of classical mechanics. One has partial derivatives (d/dx , d/dt) in an equation describing a problem, but there is a kind of decoupling of changes in x and t . There is still a relationship related to frequencies between the decoupled time and space functions as the wave-equation contains both d/dt d/dt and d/dx d/dx , but one does not have a scenario of x depending directly on t as in classical mechanics. This, we argue, leads to wave or a periodic type behaviour for both x and t . In the case of a potential $V(x)$, there can be multiple x waves $\exp(ipx)$ stirred up. In the time-independent Schrodinger equation one does not even consider time (one has $EW(x)$) even though it is clearly present through $\exp(iEt)$, but x and t are not linked

As a result, we argue that p and x are not linked because $p=mv$ and if one had $v(x)$, one could integrate $dt = dx/v(x)$ to find an explicit relationship between x and t , as in classical mechanics, which negates the idea of wave mechanics. Thus, we argue that it is the “decoupling” of space and time that is important in quantum mechanics

Schrodinger Equation from the Classical Action

The classical action: $\int L dt$, where L is the Lagrangian, may be varied with respect to trajectories to find a stationary solution as is done in classical mechanics. The resulting differential equation may be solved to find a direct relationship between x and t . This seems to be a main idea of classical mechanics which follows a trajectory. There are, however, also mechanical waves in classical physics, such as waves on a string. Even though Newton's law $dp/dt = F$ (which follows the change of p in terms of t) may be applied, the resulting wave equation:

$$d/dt d/dt W - 1/cc d/dx d/dx W = 0 \quad ((1))$$

allows for a decoupling of x and t in a certain sense because $W(x,t)=W1(x)W2(t)$. One may choose a periodic function such that the second derivative of time or x returns the function (e.g. $\sin(\omega t)$, $\sin(kx)$). Another way to consider this is to argue that derivatives are present but x and t are decoupled. What then directs changes in x and t ? It seems that a periodic solution is one which may have changes, but also contains invariance i.e. is not directed. This, we argue, is an idea associated with waves.

For a wave on a string, one thinks strictly in terms of a spatial profile e.g. $\sin(kx)$ at its peak, or a time profile describing the motion of the string up and down, ignoring x points. Thus, wave motion seems to separate or decouple x and t .

The classical action yields a relationship between x and t which is completely different from independent x - t wave behaviour. Interestingly, one may vary x and t independently (in $v=x/t$) and find relationships related to E and p i.e.

$$L = -m_0 \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} \quad \text{Action} = -m_0 c t \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} \quad dL/dt = -E \quad \text{and} \quad dL/dx = p \quad ((1))$$

In other words, changing t in L leads to energy without considering x and changing L with respect to x leads to p without any consideration of t . If one links E and p through a conservation equation:

$$E^2 = p^2 c^2 + m_0^2 c^4 \quad ((2))$$

Then one may obtain a wave type equation (the Klein-Gordon equation):

$$\frac{d^2}{dt^2} W = \frac{d^2}{dx^2} W + m_0^2 c^4 W \quad \text{where } W = \exp(i \text{Action}) \quad ((3))$$

In fact $\exp(i \text{Action})$ may be written as $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ which is a wave type solution.

Case of a Photon

A wave equation for a photon may be obtained from Maxwell's equation, by eliminating charge sources and currents. Often in classical electrodynamics, one considers a charge either moving with a constant speed or accelerating. One applies Newton's second law to this motion and explicitly links x and t . This link is carried over when calculating $E(\mathbf{r}, t)$ (the electric field) and $B(\mathbf{r}, t)$, the magnetic field. Thus, the classical idea of x being linked to t is present in the calculation of these fields. Removing the charge source and current essentially removes the classical link between x and t (of the moving charge). There are, however, still derivatives d/dt and d/dx in Maxwell's equations i.e.

$$-dB/dt = \text{grad} \times E \quad \text{and} \quad dE/dt = \text{grad} \times B \quad ((4))$$

One may ask, however, what directs a direct link or coupling between x and t (which used to be provided by the classical motion of the source charge)? It seems that there is none, but a solution must change in x and t . It can do so with x and t independent and periodic ($\sin(\omega t)$, $\sin(kx)$) i.e. a wave type solution. We argue that for $\exp(-i\omega t)\exp(ikx)$, one does not necessarily need to think in terms of a phase velocity. This, it seems, is an attempt to go back to classical mechanics and link x with t . We stress the independence of decoupling of x and t .

Quantum Bound State

To see the full separation of x and t , one may consider a bound state problem which produces a resonance i.e. a bound state. The time portion of the wavefunction is $\exp(iEt)$ which is completely separated from x (except for the fact that E , the energy, plays a role in an equation containing x , namely the Schrodinger equation). Thus, it is energy (or frequency from $\exp(iEt)$) which is the important feature, not time.

For the spatial portion, $\exp(ipx)$ no longer suffices as $V(x)$ can knock one momentum state into another. Thus, one might expect:

$$P(p/x) = a(p)\exp(ipx) / W(x) \text{ where } W(x) = \sum \text{over } p a(p)\exp(ipx) = \text{normalization function} \quad ((5))$$

Given bound state quantum mechanics, it is often noted that $a(p)a(p) = P(p)$ is the probability to find a momentum p . $P(p)$ does not depend on x i.e. if one knows p exactly, one knows nothing of x . We argue that this follows from the decoupling of x and t . If one had a relationship of the form $p(x)$, then $m \, dx/dt = p(x)$ and $t = \int 1/m \, dx/p(x)$. This would contradict t and x being decoupled or independent. Thus, it seems there may be an underlying idea, i.e. the decoupling of x and t , which governs the Heisenberg uncertainty relations.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that one may have physical situations described by an equation containing both d/dx and d/dt , but with x and t decoupled or independent. In such a case, what is driving the "change" in either x or t ? If there is no direct source, it seems there should be a kind of invariance. We argue that a periodic solution may fit such a scenario. Examples include the classical wave equation $d/dt \, d/dt \, W - 1/cc \, d/dx \, d/dx \, W = 0$, the Klein-Gordon equation: $d/dt \, d/dt \, W = d/dx \, d/dx \, W + m \, W$ and the time-independent Schrodinger equation without a potential $d/dt \, W = -1/2m \, d/dx \, d/dx \, W$. All of these are linked to $\exp(-iEt)\exp(ikx)$ solutions which allow for independent periodic motion in t and x , although E and k are linked.

In a quantum bound state, one may see the decoupling of x and t clearly as the t related solution is $\exp(iEt)$ which contains no x . It is the energy E (which is like a frequency) which influences the spatial solution. Instead of having $\exp(ipx)$, one has an ensemble i.e. $P(p/x) = a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$ where $W(x) = \sum \text{over } p a(p)\exp(ipx)$.

It is interesting to note that the decoupling of x and t may be applied at the level of the classical Action = $\int L \, dt$. By finding a stationary solution of the Action, one may obtain a differential equation yielding $x(t)$, i.e. a direct link between x and t , which seems to be a main idea of classical mechanics. If one treats x and t as being independent in $v = x/t$ (i.e. breaking with classical mechanics) one finds $d/dt \, \text{Action} = -E$ and $d/dx \, \text{Action} = p$. Thus, $\exp(i \, \text{Action})$ is equivalent to $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ and one may establish a wave equation (e.g. the Klein-Gordon equation) with $\exp(i \, \text{Action})$

References

Ruggeri, Francesco R. The Klein-Gordon Equation, $\exp(i\text{Action})$ [Propagator] and Fluctuations (preprint, zenodo, 2021)